

The New Iraqi Journal of Medicine

The Official Journal of the Iraqi Ministry of Health

Volume 3 Number 3 December 2007

The New Iraqi Journal of Medicine has agreed the use of the uniform requirements of manuscripts submitted to biomedical journals published by the INTERNATIONAL COMMITTEE OF MEDICAL JOURNAL EDITORS (ICMJE) and it's the first Iraqi peer-review medical journal listed by the ICMJE journal list. The first two issues of this journal appeared under the title of Al Karkh journal of Medicine

Executive Editor: Minister of Health
Saleh M. Al-Hasnawi

Founding Editor: Aamir Jalal Al Mosawi
Member World Association of Medical Editors

www.newiraqim.4t.com

Indexed by Copernicus Index Journal Master List and EMR index medicus

Copyright© Iraqi Ministry Of Health

Comparison of 1999 and 2003 current cigarette smoking behavior among Jordanian adolescents: the Global Youth Tobacco Surveys

Emmanuel Rudatsikira¹, Imad Al-Doghim², Adamson S. Muula³, Seter Siziya⁴

¹Departments of Global Health, Epidemiology and Biostatistics, School of Public Health, Loma Linda University, Loma Linda, California, United States of America.

²Jordanian Royal Medical Services, Amman, Jordan.

³Department of Community Health, University of Malawi, College of Medicine, Blantyre, Malawi

⁴Department of Community Medicine, University of Zambia, School of Medicine, Lusaka, Zambia

Abstract

Background: Adolescent cigarette smoking has received particular attention in the past two decades. Comparison of prevalence estimates trends is likely to inform public health intervention strategies. This study was conducted to compare the prevalence of current cigarette smoking among school going adolescents in Jordan between 1999 and 2003.

Methods: Cross sectional, questionnaire-based study among school going adolescents in the Jordanian Global Youth Tobacco Survey 1999 and 2003.

Email addresses of authors

ER: erudatsikira@llu.edu

AA: aldoghim@hotmail.com

ASM: muula@email.unc.edu

SS: ssiziya@yahoo.com

Address correspondence: Dr. Adamson S. MUULA, Department of Community Health, University of Malawi, College of Medicine, Private Bag 360, Blantyre 3, Malawi. Email: muula@email.unc.edu

Results: The overall prevalence of smoking in 1999 was 16.9% (95% CI 15.7%-18.1%) versus 15.5% (95% CI 14.5-16.5) in 2003. In terms of gender distribution 26.9% (95% CI 24.5%-29.3%) males were current smokers in 1999, while 20.0% (18.4%-21.6%) were smokers in 2003. 12.4% (95% CI 10.3%-14.5%) females were smokers in 1999 and 10.1% (95% CI 8.9%-11.2%) females were smokers in 2003. Thus comparing the 1999 estimates to the 2003 suggests that there has been an overall drop in prevalence of current smoking among school going adolescents in Jordan.

Conclusion: Widespread antismoking public health interventions may have resulted in the observed reduction in current smoking prevalence in Jordan between 1999 and 2003. There is need to continue monitoring the trends in smoking among adolescents.

Keywords: adolescents, cigarette, smoking, Jordan, non-communicable diseases

Background

Tobacco is the single most important preventable cause of cardiovascular morbidity and cancers in the world [1-4]. Many adult smokers initiate the habit as adolescents. Adolescent smoking is also of public health significance as smoking is a marker of many other harmful lifestyles [5-7].

Akpınar et al [8] have reported prevalence of 26.6% among 13 year olds and 43.7% among 17 years olds in Turkey. In Syria, prevalence of adult cigarette smoking was reported at 56.9% and 35.3% among adult males and women [9]. The Centers for Disease Control and Prevention has reported that 21% and 2.1% of male and female adolescents in Kurdistan Region of Iraq were smokers in 2005 [10].

Much of the data on cigarette smoking in Jordan among young people have mostly come from studies in which study participants were university students or patients attending dental services [11,12]. While these studies could be representative of their respective source populations, they are unlikely to be representative of the adolescent general population.

Two waves of the Global Youth Tobacco Survey (GYTS) were done in Jordan (1999 and 2003) using the GYTS standard methodology [13-14] to estimate the prevalence of tobacco use and associated factors among school-going adolescents. The GYTS Collaborating Group and Warren et al. have reported prevalence of current smoking among adolescents in 1999 in Jordan as 16.6% [15,16]. While cross national comparisons of the prevalence

of adolescent cigarette smoking have been conducted before [14, 17,18], there is little information about same country comparison over the years. The objective of this study was to compare the prevalence of cigarette smoking among school going adolescents in Jordan in 1999 and 2003. We also assessed whether there had been changes in the number of cigarettes smoked per day by adolescents who were current cigarette smokers.

Methods

Our study was secondary analysis of the data obtained from the Jordanian Global Youth Tobacco Survey. A comprehensive description of the GYTS methodology has been reported elsewhere [20-21]. In brief, the GYTS is a cross sectional school-based survey of students aimed at ages 13–15 years. Two-stage sample design strategy is used in which schools are selected proportional to their enrollment size. Within any selected school, random selection of classes is done. All students within the selected classes are eligible to participation regardless of their actual ages. A standardized questionnaire is self-completed anonymously by the students and it takes students between 30 to 40 minutes to complete. The questionnaire is aimed at collecting the following information among young people: cigarette smoking and other tobacco use; knowledge and attitudes of towards cigarette smoking; role of the media and advertising and their use of cigarettes; access to cigarettes; tobacco-related school curriculum; exposure to environmental tobacco smoke (ETS) and cessation of cigarette smoking. For the purpose of this study however, only data related to estimation of prevalence of current cigarette smoking, gender distribution of

current smoking and number of cigarettes smoked per day will be reported.

Current smoking is defined as having ever smoked even one puff in the past 30 days. The question asked was: "During the past 30 days, have you smoked part or all of a cigarette?" The number of cigarettes smoked was assessed by asking the question: "During the past 30 days (one month), on the days you smoked, how many cigarettes did you smoke?"

A weighting factor was used in the analysis to obtain prevalence of the outcome to reflect the likelihood of sampling each student and to reduce bias by compensating for differing patterns of non response. The weight used for estimation is given by the following formula:

$W = W1 * W2 * f1 * f2 * f3 * f4$, where
W1 = the inverse of the probability of selecting the school
W2 = the inverse of the probability of selecting the classroom within the school
f1 = a school-level non response adjustment factor calculated by school size category (small, medium, large)
f2 = a class-level non response adjustment factor calculated for each school
f3 = a student-level non response adjustment factor calculated by class
f4 = a post stratification adjustment factor calculated by grade.

Ethical considerations

Permission to conduct the study was obtained from the relevant authorities within the Ministries of Health and Education. Participation by the eligible students was voluntary. Data collection was conducted in school by trained assistants and questionnaires were administered without the presence of their teachers.

Data Analysis

Data were analyzed using SUDAAN 9.0 (Research Triangle Institute, Research Triangle Park, Durham, North Carolina, USA). Proportions and 95% confidence intervals (CI) were obtained as estimates of prevalence. Chi-square tests were used to compare the proportions. An α value was set at 0.05 and so p value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Since the age distribution of study participants between the two survey waves was different, the two study groups were not comparable in this regard. As prevalence of smoking in part is dependent on age, there was need to standardize the estimates before meaningful comparisons could be done. The following formula was used:

$$(\sum P_j * A_j) / N * 100$$

where P_j = 1999 age specific prevalence of current smoking for age j

A_j = number of participants in age category j in 2003

N = total number of study participants in 2003

The 100 in the denominator is required when prevalence P_j is reported as %, otherwise if P_j is reported as ranging from 0 to 1, the 100 in the denominator is not required.

Results

3912 adolescents participated in the 1999 survey. Information of gender was available for 3681 (94.1%). Of those who had data available 1682 (45.7%) were males and (54.3%) were females in 1999. In 2003, 6313 students participated and information on gender was available for 5838 (92.5%) participants. Of these 2874 (51.2%) were males and 2964 (50.8%) were females. The median age in both 1999 and 2003 surveys was 14 years. However, the age distribution of study

participants between the two survey years was different as shown in table 1.

Table 1: Age distribution of study participants in 1999 and 2003

Age	Frequency (%)	
	1999	2003
11 or younger	353 (8.9)	403 (7.2)
12	472 (11.8)	295 (5.5)
13	1043 (25.0)	520 (9.2)
14	1059 (26.5)	1640 (26.5)
15	745 (22.1)	1523 (25.2)
16	141 (4.3)	1414 (23.4)
17 or older	49 (1.4)	189 (3.1)
Total	3862	5984

Prevalence of current cigarette smoking .The overall prevalence of smoking in 1999 was 16.9% (95% CI 15.7-18.1) versus 15.5% (95% CI 14.5-16.5) in 2003. In terms of gender distribution 26.9% (95% CI 24.5-29.3) males were current smokers in 1999, while 20.0% (18.4-21.6) were smokers in 2003. 12.4% (95% CI 10.3-14.5) females were smokers in 1999 and 10.1% (8.9-11.2) females were smokers in 2003.

Age-specific current cigarette smoking

We also aimed to compare the age-distributed current cigarette smoking prevalence between 1999 and 2003. The results are reported in table 2.

Table 2: Age-specific current cigarette smoking prevalence among adolescents in Jordan 1999 and 2003

Age category in yrs	1999 Prevalence	2003 Prevalence	p value
11 yrs or younger	19.3	20.8	0.08
12	19.6	34.1	<0.01 *
13	13.8	20.5	0.08
14	15.8	14.2	0.02*
15	20.6	20.5	0.45
16	36.2	24.9	<0.01 *
>=17	42.6	35.9	0.54

*statistically significant at $\alpha= 0.05$

When the 1999 overall prevalence (18.7%) was standardized to the 2003 age distribution, the prevalence was 22.0% and was statistically significantly different from the 2003 estimate ($p<0.01$).

We also aimed to assess whether there has been a change in the number of cigarette smoked on each smoking days by the adolescent smoker. There was a statistical difference in the number of cigarettes smoked per day between the 1999 and 2003 surveys as reported in table 3. However there was no general pattern observed.

Table 3: Number of cigarette smoked per day among current adolescent cigarette smokers in Jordan 1999 and 2003

Number of Cigarettes per day	1999 Prevalence in %	2003 Prevalence in %	p-value
< 1	46.6	28.3	<0.01
1	28.0	24.8	<0.10
2 to 5	13.9	22.4	<0.01
6 to 10	6.2	11.6	<0.01
11 to 20	3.7	6.4	<0.01
>20	1.7	6.6	<0.01

Discussion

The prevalence of current cigarette smoking among school-going adolescents in Jordan was 16.9% in 1999 and 24.6% in 2003. Our 1999 current smoking prevalence estimate is different from the 16.6% reported by the Global Youth Tobacco Survey Collaborative Group (GYTSG) in 2002 using the same data [15]. The reason for the difference was that the GYTSG calculated the prevalence figure as number of participants reporting current smoking divided by total number of study participants. In our estimate, the numerator was the same as in the GYTSG but the denominator was only those who completed the question on current smoking. In the 1999 survey 172 (4.4%)

did not the answer the question: "During the past 30 days, have you smoked part or all of a cigarette?" Including these study participants within the denominator was similar to assuming that they were all non-smokers. We chose to use only complete case analysis, and so our estimate is slightly higher, although the difference with the GYTSG was not statistically significant.

The prevalence of smoking in 1999 at 16.9% was only slightly higher than 15.5% estimated in 2003, $p= 0.40$. However if the 1999 prevalence was age-standardized to the 2003 sample, the prevalence of cigarette smoking rises to 22.0% ($p<0.01$). This suggests that the prevalence estimate in the earlier sample was statistically different from the 2003 sample, if the age distributional differences between the samples are considered.

The Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) has reported an overall current smoking prevalence

among school going adolescents in the Eastern Mediterranean region as 15.3% [14]. Our estimates are not far different from the 'average' prevalence for the region. This suggests that most countries in the region have relatively high prevalence of smoking.

The decrease in current smoking prevalence in Jordan could be explained, partly if not to a great extent by the public health interventions that the Kingdom of Jordan has taken over the past several

years [22]. In 1998, the Jordanian government put in place anti-smoking legislation to prohibit smoking in public places, it has banned the advertisement of cigarettes in the media, and a national committee has been established to draw-up strategies and programs to combat smoking. In 2001, the government used postage stamps to carry adolescent relevant antismoking messages. The committee on the prevention of smoking in Jordan has wide representation including Health Ministry, UNICEF, the Public Security Department, Jordan Bar Association, the National Anti-Smoking Society and the Ministry of Awqaf and Islamic Affairs.

We also aimed to assess whether there was a change among current cigarette smokers with regard to number of cigarettes smoked per day. The proportion of smokers smoking less than a cigarette a day to 5 cigarettes a day were higher in 1999 as compared to 2003. However the proportion having at least 6 cigarettes per day were significantly higher in 2003. This may suggest that although overall smoking prevalence in 2003 was lower than in 1999, the proportion of smokers taking higher numbers of cigarettes increased over the period. Considering that there is an increasing dose-response association between the number of cigarettes and adverse health outcomes, a significant proportion of adolescents were exposing themselves to greater potential harm in 2003. It is also important to recognize that adolescents who smoke cigarettes may also be engaging in other unhealthy behaviours [23]. A holistic approach to overall healthy living is therefore likely to be of greater public health significance than individual behaviour approach.

This study has a number of limitations. The data used were obtained through self-completed questionnaire. There is a possibility that some study participants may have misreported their exposure status. However, Brener et al has assessed a method of data collection the GYTS in the United States and they have reported high reliability [24]. While reliability of data collection instrument was acceptable in the United States, we are not aware as to whether the methodology also has high reliability in the Eastern Mediterranean region. We suggest that future studies assess such issues.

Also by asking how many cigarettes the adolescent smoked on the days s/he smoked assumed that the adolescent would smoke a regular number of cigarettes each day. This may result in mis-classification based due to recall problems. It is also not known whether all or some study participants responded thinking that the researchers were asking for the 'average' number of cigarettes per smoking day. Obviously some study participants may have smoked more on certain days and not much on others.

Another limitation of the GYTS methodology is that self reported history of current smoking is not verified by biomarkers such as salivary or blood cotinine level or exhaled carbon monoxide [25-27]. We suggest that the Global Youth Tobacco Survey Collaborating Group consider validating the questionnaire with biomarkers in future surveys. As the GYTS methodology only allows recruitment of students who are present in school on the day that the survey is administered, our findings may not be applicable to all students. Also the findings may not be applicable to out-of school adolescents.

In between the two initiatives, the Jordanian National Anti-Smoking Strategy has been launched [28]. It is expected that such initiatives will support the reduction in the prevalence of smoking among all age groups in Jordan.

Conclusion

We find that the overall prevalence of current cigarette among adolescents who participated in the Jordanian Global Youth Tobacco Survey in 1999 was much higher than that obtained in 2003. We suggest that public health interventions aimed to prevent smoking in Jordan may have started bearing fruit.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Acknowledgements

The GYTS is a collaborative project of WHO/CDC/participating countries. Analyses of GYTS data are not necessarily endorsed by the WHO/CDC/participating countries. We are grateful also to Drs Mohammed Shreim and Ayub Hiba for coordinating the Global Youth Tobacco Surveys in Jordan.

References

- 1- Ansary-Moqhaddam A, Huxley R, Barzi F et al. The effect of modifiable risk factors on pancreatic mortality in populations of the Asia Pacific region. *Cancer Epidemiol Biomarker Prev* 2006; 15: 2435-40.
- 2- Brand RM, Jones DD, Lynch HT, Brand RE, Watson P, Ashwathnayan R, Roy HK. Risk of colon cancer in hereditary non-polyposis colorectal cancer patients as predicted by fuzzy modeling: influence of smoking. *World J Gastroenterol* 2006; 12: 4485-91.
- 3- Kaur J, Bains K. A study of the risk factor profile of cardiovascular diseases in rural Punjabi male patients. *Indian J Public Health* 2006; 50(2):97-100.
- 4- Toustad S, Andrew-Johnston J. Cardiovascular risks associated with smoking: a review for clinicians. *Eur J Cardiovasc Prev Rehabil* 2006; 13(4): 507-14
- 5- Rudatsikira E, Siziya S, Kazembe LN, Muula AS: Prevalence and associated factors of physical fighting among school-going adolescents in Namibia. *Ann Gen Psychiatry* 2007; 6:18.
- 6- Dierker LC, Sledjeski EM, Botello-Harbaum M, Ramirez RR, Chavez LM, Canino G: Association between psychiatric disorders and smoking stages within a representative clinic sample of Puerto Rican adolescents. *Compr Psychiatry* 2007; 48:237-44.
- 7- Haddad LG, Malak MZ. Smoking habits and attitudes towards smoking among university students in Jordan. *Int J Nurs Stud* 2002; 39: 793-802.
- 8- Akpınar E, Yoldascan E, Saatci E. The smoking prevalence and the determinants of smoking behaviour among students in Cukurova University, Southern Turkey. *West Indian Med J.* 2006;55:414-9.
- 9- Ward KD, Eissenberg T, Rastam S, Asfar T, Mzayek F, Fouad MF, Hammal F, Mock J, Maziak W. The tobacco epidemic in Syria. *Tob Control.* 2006 ;15 Suppl 1:i24-9
- 10- Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC). Tobacco use among students aged 13-15 years--Kurdistan Region, Iraq, 2005. *MMWR Morb Mortal Wkly Rep.* 2006 26;55:556-9.
- 11- Alomari Q, Barrieshi-Nusair K, Said K. Smoking prevalence and its effect on dental attitudes and behaviour among dental students. *Med Princ Pract* 2006; 15: 195-9.
- 12- Kyrlesli A, Soteriades ES, Warren CW, Kremastinou J, Papastergiou P, Jones NR, Hadjichristodoulou C. Tobacco use among students aged 13-15 years in Greece: the GYTS project. *BMC Public Health.* 2007;7:3.
- 13- Arora M, Reddy KS. Global Youth Tobacco Survey (GYTS) - Delhi. *Indian Pediatr* 2005;42:850-1.
- 14- Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC). Use of cigarettes and other tobacco products among students aged 13-15 years--worldwide, 1999-2005. *MMWR Morb Mortal Wkly Rep.* 2006;55:553-6.
- 15- Global Youth Tobacco Survey Collaborative Group. Tobacco use among youth: a cross country

- comparison. *Tob Control* 2002;11:252-70.
- 16- Warren CW, Riley L, Asma S, Eriksen MP, Green L, Blanton C, Loo C, Batchelor S, Yach D. Tobacco use by youth: a surveillance report from the Global Youth Tobacco Survey project. *Bull World Health Organ* 2000;78:868-76.
 - 17- Global Youth Tobacco Survey Collaborating Group. Differences in worldwide tobacco use by gender: findings from the Global Youth Tobacco Survey. *J Sch Health* 2003;73:207-15.
 - 18- Muula AS, Mpabulungi L. Cigarette smoking prevalence among school-going adolescents in two African capital cities: Kampala Uganda and Lilongwe Malawi. *Afr Health Sci* 2007;7:45-9.
 - 19- Global Tobacco Surveillance System Collaborating Group. Global Tobacco Surveillance System (GTSS): purpose, production, and potential. *J Sch Health*. 2005;75:15-24.
 - 20- Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC). Use of cigarettes and other tobacco products among students aged 13-15 years--worldwide, 1999-2005. *MMWR Morb Mortal Wkly Rep* 2006;55: 553-6.
 - 21- Rudatsikira E, Abdo A, Muula AS. Prevalence and determinants of adolescent tobacco smoking in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia. *BMC Public Health* 2007;7:176.
 - 22- Kandela P. Jordan starts campaign to tackle high rates of smoking. *Lancet* 2000; 355: 1800
 - 23- Miller JW, Naimi TS, Brewer RD, Jones SE. Binge drinking and associated health risk behaviours among high school students. *Pediatrics* 2007; 119: 76-85.
 - 24- Brener ND, Kann L, McMannus T, Kinchen SA, Sundberg EC, Ross JG. Reliability of the 1999 youth risk behaviors survey questionnaire. *J Adolesc Health* 2002;31: 336-42.
 - 25- Hung J, Lin CH, Wang JD, Chann CC: Exhaled carbon monoxide level as an indicator of cigarette consumption in a workplace cessation program in Taiwan. *J Formos Med Assoc* 2006; 105: 210-3.
 - 26- Jenkins RA, Counts RW: Personal exposure to environmental tobacco smoke: salivary cotinine, airborne nicotine, and nonsmoker misclassification. *J Expo Anal Environ Epidemiol* 1999; 9: 352-63.
 - 27- Low EC, Ong MC, Tan M: Breath carbon monoxide as an indication of smoking habit in the military setting. *Singapore Med J* 2001; 45:578- 82.
 - 28- Jordan Times. National Anti-smoking strategy to be announced today. May 2, 2002 accessed on 26 September 2007 from <http://www.jordanembassyus.org/05302002006.htm>